

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

NO_x should be recycled by stoping of NO_x elimination by ammonia. Waste water purification center should be closed

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Abstract

Global warming is caused by the lack of N and P and decrease of CO₂ assimilation and decrease of CO₂ fix and decrease of heat absorption. Lack of N and P is caused by the elimination of NO_x and NP in waste water. Fish production at Seto inland sea decreased 90% by the lack of N and P.

Global warming will stop if developed countries stop the elimination of NO_x and NP. CO₂ assimilation will be activated and Global warming will stop.

The author presented petition to stop the elimination of NO_x by ammonia and to close waste water purification center. If developed countries stop the elimination of NO_x by ammonia and close waste water purification. CO₂ assimilation is activated and Global warming will stop

Keywords: NO_x; CO₂ assimilation; NO_x elimination by ammonia; Carbon neutral; Stop of global warming; GWPR

1. Introduction

Global warming is in progress. CO₂ concentration is increasing 20 ppm every year. Increase of CO₂ is caused by the decrease of CO₂ assimilation. Decrease of CO₂ assimilation is caused by the lack of nitrogen (N) and phosphorous (P). Lack of N and P is caused by the elimination of N and P in waste water and elimination of NO_x by the insertion of ammonia into exit gas. Concentration of N,P decreased. Growth of plankton decreased. Fish production of Japan decreased from 12 million tone to 4 million tone. Author suggested the reasons and method to protect global warming by 60 papers (ref 1-60). But global warming is progressing. Then author presented petition (61,62) to ask the stopping of ammonia addition to the exit gas and asked closure of waste water clean center.

Conference of 7 developed countries decided the elimination of NO_x in exit gas and elimination of N,P in waste water. They tried to eliminate NO_x by the reaction of ammonia.

Japan set up waste water purification center. And eliminated N,P.

The author published 60 papers against this policy. But Japan government do not follow my opinion. And continuing their policy and global warming is in progress.

Then I presented petition (ref 91) to the Tokyo Regional court civil matter department demanding

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The abolition of following two laws

- Protection of air pollution
- Protection law to protect water quality

Defender Kishida Fumio prime minister

But this petition is rejected by the reason prime minister cannot be a defender.

Then author presented new petition (ref 62) demanding

- Stop NO_x elimination by stopping the addition of ammonia in to the exit gas.
- Close waste water purification center
- Send this petition to defender and read the attached document carefully. Open oral arguments

Defender Nishimura Akihiro Minister of the Environment

Ministry of the environment is set up around 1985 . And they are trying to purify water and air and they inhibited the release of waste water containing nitrogen and phosphorous compound. They set up 2200 waste water purification center and N and P is made to activated sludge. Ocean dumping of disposal of human excreta is inhibited. As the result, concentrated of N and P in sea decreased, and CO₂ assimilation decreased and production of plankton and fish decreased. Waste water purification center should be closed.

Seven developed countries disliked NO_x in exit gas of car as toxic substance. They extend their idea to the exit gas of electricity generation plant. They tried to eliminate NO_x by the reaction with ammonia

CO₂ produced at developed countries is around 10 billion tone. And around $10 \times \frac{1}{25} = 4$ hundred million tone NO_x is produced. 400 hundred million tone NO_x is eliminating by 227 million tone NH₃ every year. This gave big damage for developed countries This reaction should not be done. Ammonia addition to the exit gas should be stoped.

2. Waste water clean center should be closed

Japan constructed 2200 waste water purification center to eliminate NP. Author investigated Yamazaki waste water purification center at Yamazaki, Kamakura in Japan (ref 38). This center cover 96881 persons. Water 98287 m³ containing Nitrogen 40 mg/l, Phosphorous 4.2 mg/l is treated by activated sludge process. Air is bubbled for ten hours to give water contains Nitrogen 7.5 mg/l ,Phosphorous 2.73 mg/l. Consuming 8841200kWh electricity. Population of Japan is 120 million.

This data showed that if Japan stop waste water clean center 44900 tone Nitrogen, 174 00 tone Phosphorus can work as fertilizer Phosphorous is eliminated in one day at this center. This data indicate $7.34 \times \frac{120000000}{96881 \times 365} = 140$ million tone Nitrogen, 12.8 million tone Phosphorous can work as fertilizer in one year. $140 \times 25 = 3200$ million tone CO₂ is fixed and 3200 million tone plankton can grow and $3200 \times \frac{1}{10} = 3.5$ million = 35tone fish will be produced. By stopping of waste water purification center, consumption of $884100 \times \frac{1200000000}{96881} = 110$ billion kWh electricity($\frac{100880}{110} = 1.11\%$ of total electricity consumption 1000880 kWh of Japan)is saved. For the generation of electricity, 59000 tone CH₄ is used. By stopping of waste water purification, baying of 590000 tone CH₄ become unnecessary and $590000 \times 3 = 1770000$ t CO₂ emission will stop. Each house must pay waste water purification fee(about 30 \$ in addition to water fee. If waste water clean center is closed, we need not pay waste water purification fee. If waste water purification is not done in Japan , $140 \times 25 = 35$ million tone CO₂ is fixed and 35 million tone plankton can grow and $35 \times \frac{1}{10} = 3.5$ million tone fish will be produced. Therefore waste water clean center should be closed.

Phosphorous and nitrogen eliminations of the world will be 10 times of Japan. If developed countries stop the elimination of nitrogen and phosphorous by stopping of waste water purification center , 82950 tone fish will be produced. And 121660 tone CO₂ will be fixed.

- Nitrogen $3318 \times 10 = 33180$ tone
- Phosphorous $318 \times 10 = 3180$ tone.
- Then $33180 \times 25 = 82950$ tone fish
- $82950 \times \frac{44}{30} = 121660$ tone CO₂

2.1. Elimination of NO_x in exit gas by ammonia should be stopped.

NO_x is a gift from nature. NO_x is produced by thunder NO_x is produced when some thing is burned. NO_x is natural fertilizer. Seven developed countries mis estimated the utility and toxicity of NO_x. NO_x is not toxic when NO_x is released at open air. NO_x is necessary compound for CO₂ assimilation(ref 7). NO_x must be recycled. But conference of 7 developed countries decided to eliminate NO_x by the reaction with ammonia.

Developed countries are eliminating NO_x and nitrogen and phosphorous and CO₂ assimilation is blocked and CO₂fix is reduced . CO₂ is increasing.

The author realized that this reaction is the main reason of global warming. This reaction is the reaction of one nitrogen compound with other nitrogen compound to give N₂. For the preparation of ammonia, much CH₄ is necessary (ref 50-55).

CO₂ produced at developed countries is around 10 billion tone. And around 10x 1/25 = 4 hundred million tone NO_x is produced. To eliminate this NO (90% of NO_x is NO), 226 million tone ammonia NH₃ is used. Amount of NO_x is so much . Elimination of NO_x use much ammonia and natural gas. These decision give great damage for agriculture and fish industry , GDP and protection of global warming.

NO_x is eliminated by ammonia. Ammonia is produced by the reaction of nitrogen and hydrogen. Hydrogen is produced by the reaction of methane with water.

To make 226.2 mills NH₃, 400 mill t H₂ is used.

To make 400 mill tone H₂, 80000 mill t CH₄ is used. And 220 mill t CO₂ is produced.

Government of developed country asked the addition of ammonia to the exit gas of factory by the ratio of 400 mill tone NO_x to 226.7 mill tone ammonia If factory do not follow this rule, they cannot operate the factory Amount of NO_x and ammonia is huge . Japan is keeping this arrangement most honestly. Then NO_x concentration in exit gas of Japan is lowest 0.1 g/kWh ,USA is 0.5 g/kWh ,Germany 0.31 g/kWh and China,India, Indonesia (no NO_x elimination country) are 1.6 g/kWh.. GDP ratio 2021/1991 USA is 3.2, Japan 1.1, Germany 4.3, Developed countries use much fossil to eliminate NO_x The price of electricity is high and productive industry moved to developing countries. These countries increased GDP. 2021/1991 China 51.1,India 11.1. No NO_x elimination country use NO_x as fertilizer and getting much food and fixing all CO₂ produced at his country. GWPR of developed countries is over 1. Japan is 3.3. and criticized as carbon country. The price of electricity differ greatly by doing NO_x elimination or not. Developing country like China 1.4-4.3 c/kWh, India, 6 c /kWh,Indonesia 10 c/ kWh. Developed countries who eliminate NO_x USA 10 c/kWh, Japan 24 c/kWh,Germany 33 c/kWh,UK 15.4 c/IWh,Italy 28 c/kWh.

If developed country stop the addition of ammonia to the exit gas, Consumption of 8000 million tone CH₄ can be saved. And emission of 220 million tone CO₂ can be saved. And 400 mill t x 25 = 10 billion t CO₂ can be fixed. Accordingly 220 mill t + 10 bill t = 10.22 billion tone CO₂ can be fixed. CO₂ em addition of developed countries is 10 billion tone.GWPR (CO₂em)/ (CO₂fix) = 1.

Therefore, CO₂ increase is zero. 10.22 billion Tone CO₂ produce plant like wheat. CO₂ produce plant 2/3 30(1/6 of molecular weight of C₆ H₂0 O₆) /44 Molecular weight of CO₂) weight of his weight. Wheat contain 2/3 straw of his

weight Wheat grain will be about 1/3 weight of plant. 10.22 billion Tone CO₂ can afford 10.22 billion x 30/44 x 1/3 = 2.32 billion tone grain. 1kg wheat is 1.5 \$ 2.32 billion kg wheat is 3.48billion \$. Therefore, if developed country do not eliminate NP. 2.32 billion Tone wheat. 3.48 billion\$ is produced. GDP will increase. Economy of developed country will become much better. And global warming will not happen

At this moment Japan is using 28.33 mill tone ammonia and global warming is progressing. Global warming must stop sooner. Therefore author presented petition asking to stop the addition of ammonia into exit gas

In Japan 125 million tone CO₂ and 1250x1/25= 50 million tone NO_x (90 % is NO) is produced. Recycle of nitrogen and phosphorous is necessary. If we stop the addition of ammonia and stop the supply of electricity to clean center. Then following damage will be recovered.

To eliminate NO_x, 28.33 million tone NH₃ is used.

To make 28.33 mill tone ammonia, 5 mill t hydrogen is used.

To make 5 mill t H₂, 10 mill t CH₄ is used and 27.5 mill t CO₂ is produced

Japan is eliminating 50 mill t NO_x by spending 10 mill t LNG emitting 27.5 mill t CO₂.

If Japan do not eliminate NO_x, Japan can fix 50 x 25 = 1250 mill t CO₂.

CO₂ grow plankton 2/3 of his weight (30 1/6 of molecular weight C₆H₁₂O₆ /44 CO₂ molecular weight). Fish grow by eating 10 times of plankton. 10 bill t CO₂ fix mean 10x 3/4x1/10 = 7.5 bill kg fish production. Fish price is 2 \$ per kg. 2x 75 = 150 billion \$. But by the elimination of NO_x, 150 billion \$ fish was not produced. Japan was producing 12 mill t fish and 4 mill t rice before 1980 at that time no elimination. By the elimination of NP only 4 million fishes were produced. Fisherman 388990 in 1963 decreased to 151700 in 2018. Country region is suffering from depression and depopulation. GDP does not increase since NP elimination has started. The elimination of NP influence not only warm up earth but also give significant bud influence on economy. If elimination of NO_x by blow in ammonia to the exit gas stopped and elimination of NP in waste water stoped, around 10x 1/25 = 4 hundred million tone NO_x is produced. 4x25 = 100 hundred million tone (10 billion tone) grain will be produced.

3. Comparison of GWPR and GDP at developed countries and developing countries

Developed countries are emitting about 10 billion tone CO₂ and emitting 400 million tone. NO_x. 400 million tone NO_x is destroyed by 226.2 mill tone ammonia. 226.2 million tone is produced from 400 million tone hydrogen. 400 million tone hydrogen is produced from 8000 million tone CH₄ producing 220 million tone CO₂.

It is difficult to reduce CO₂ but it is easy to reduce GWPR by increase of CO₂ fix. To increase CO₂ fix, by increase of NP. To increase NP, just stop the elimination of NP. To increase N and P, stop the elimination of NP. Developing countries like China, India and Indonesia are using NO_x and NP as fertilizer. CO₂ assimilation is promoted rapidly and production of agriculture and fish industry increased rapidly and GDP increase rate are high. On the contrary at developed country, CO₂ assimilation is inhibited and production of agriculture and fish industry is inhibited. Economic and social influence are immeasurable grate. We can compare developed country who doing NO_x, NP elimination and developing countries who use NO_x, NP as fertilizer. (ref 56-60)

CO₂em (CO₂emission), NO_x (NO_x production), NO_xc (NO_x concentration at exit gas), Dump (Wastewater dumping), Fixable CO₂, GWPR (global warming protection ratio),GDP (GDP ratio 2021/1991) of 13 countries are shown in Table 1

Table 1 CO₂ emit, NO_x,NO_xcon, Dump, FixableCO₂ GWPR,GDP of 13 countries

Country	CO ₂ emit	NO _x	NO _x con	Wdunp	FixablCO ₂	GWPR	GDP
	Hmilt	Hmillt	g/kWh		Hills		2021/1991
World	510	16.5					
China	196.4	4.25	1.6	Do	100	1.0	51.1
India	24.6	1	1.6	Do	32	0.76	11.1
Indonesia	5.0	0.2	1.6	Do	19	0.3	
USA	51	2	0.5	No	95	0.53	3.7
Japan	12	0	0	No	3.8	3.3	1.1
Russia	19.6	0.63			32	0.61	
Germany	7.6	1.0	1.0	No	2.2	2.2	4.3
UK	4.0	0.16	1.3	No	2.4	1.2	3.3
Italy	3.5	0.14	0.5	No	3.0	1.2	
France	0.12			No	6.4	0.4	
Canal	5.6	0.22	1.3	No	199	0.06	
Iran	6.3	0.025			1.6	3.0	
Turky	4.0	0.16			7.6	0.5	

Developed countries can get 174.4 billion \$, by stopping NP elimination and can get high GDP and GDP ratio 2021/ 1991 will increase as China.

Not only elimination of NO_x and NP are promoting global warming, but also retarding development of countries and industry. Japan government consider that ammonia as a substance that do not produce CO₂ and using ammonia to eliminate NO_x. CO₂ produced in Japan is 1.25 billion tone. NO_x produced in Japan is 1/25 of 1.25 billion tone, 50 million tone. Japan is eliminating 20 times of synthetic fertilizer 2.5 million tone. Then NO_x is not destroyed and CO₂ assimilation will progress and much fish and grain will be produced and GWPR will decrease and GDP will increase .

The complete recycle of nitrogen and phosphorous become possible.Sufficient supply of nitrogen and phosphorous is done and food production will increase GDP will increase. National economy and wealth will increase.

4. Conclusion

Complete recycle of nitrogen and phosphorus is necessary to stop global warming. Stopping of ammonia addition to the exit gas and closing of waste water purification center can increase NP concentration and can activate CO₂ assimilation and can produce much grain and fish and can get high GDP and growth and can stop global warming.

Compliance with ethical standards

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